

NORMATIVE REGULATION OF ACCOUNTING AND CONTROL COMMODITY TRANSACTIONS

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Annotation: In sales organizations, the main management process is sale of goods. This article defines normative regulation of accounting and control commodity transactions.

Key words: trade, management process, sale of goods, normative regulation, control commodity transactions.

Trade is one of the leading sectors of the national economy, which has a large inventory of the predominant part of the working capital of trade organizations. Correct the organization of accounting for goods and commodity transactions is of great importance for successful solution of accounting problems.

Commodity operations at wholesale and retail trade enterprises are the process of activity associated with the acquisition of goods at a favourable price and its sale at a higher price in order to obtain arrived.

In sales organizations, the main management process is sale of goods. The sales cycle in a trade organization includes complex business transactions involving the sale of goods for cash and non-cash payments, receipt of funds at the cash desk and accounts opened in banking institutions, collection of receivables, and calculation of sales expenses, taxes and profits from the sale of goods.

Thus, internal control over the process of selling goods interacts directly with internal process control payment and income. From the point of view of a trade organization, the sales process is the guide in the management of all administrative staff, management decisions are made, the processes necessary for the transfer of ownership of goods, control of sales, sales costs and formed financial result from sales.

The object of accounting in retail trade organizations are goods. Accounting for commodity transactions due to the nature of the exchange, control over the movement, safety of goods, identification of financial results, the formation of complete and reliable reporting information and is the essence of business accounting.

The main purpose of accounting for the movement of goods is ensuring control over their correct and timely receipt and posting by financially responsible persons; state and safety of inventory items; their disposal and implementation, and also by determining the financial, final result from the sale of goods.

The main production processes in trading activities are:

- the process of receiving goods;
- the process of storing goods;
- the process of selling goods.

In a trade organization, goods come mainly from suppliers. The movement of goods from the supplier to the buyer is documented enclosed documents stipulated by the supply contracts and rules for the carriage of goods. The main supporting documents issued by suppliers are the consignment note, bill of lading and invoice.

A bill of lading is a document for accounting for the movement of commodity and material assets moved with the participation vehicles and is a document accompanying the cargo.

The rule consists of two parts:

- Commodity, which determines the relationship between the consignor and consignee and is intended for debiting goods from the accounts consignor and posting to the account of the consignee.

- Transport, determining the relationship of the organization shipper ordering a vehicle with the owners vehicles carrying goods and used to calculate shipping costs.

A bill of lading is a document on which a transfer takes place. The invoice indicates the type of goods, its quantity, price, total cost. The bill of lading is affixed signatures of the transmitting and receiving parties and is a document for accounting.

The invoice is issued by the seller to the buyer after the final acceptance of the goods and is the basis for the buyer to accept VAT amounts to deduction. It contains information about the name and details of the seller and the buyer, the list of goods, their price, cost, rate and amount of VAT, other indicators.

The procedure and terms for the acceptance of goods in terms of quantity and quality and documentation are regulated by supply contracts, specifications, instructions on the procedure for acceptance of goods according to quantity, quality and completeness.

The supply agreement is one of the types of purchase and sale agreement, regulating relations between organizations engaged in production and wholesale trade of raw materials, materials, components, equipment.

A supply contract is a document of sale and purchase according to which the seller undertakes to transfer to the buyer the goods produced or purchased goods for the implementation of business activities.

Acceptance of goods by quantity includes verification of compliance the actual availability of goods to the data contained in the accompanying documents, and when accepting goods in terms of quality and completeness - the requirements set out in the contract. The procedure for receiving goods and its documentation depends on: the place of acceptance (in the warehouse supplier, from the transport organization, at the buyer's warehouse), nature acceptance (in terms of quantity, quality, completeness), degree of compliance actually received goods, the terms of the contract and the accompanying documents, the presence or absence of accompanying documents, etc.

If the responsible person receives the goods in the warehouse supplier, the necessary document is a power of attorney, special document, which is designed to confirm the rights and duties of the parties. The main purpose of a power of attorney is to confirm the authority of a trustee to a third party. The act necessarily fixes the rights and obligations that the fiduciary. Clearly defined rights and obligations avoid illegal actions on the part of the employee for whom this power of attorney.

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